

Semantic Non-Terrestrial Communications with Open RAN-enabled 6G

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Abstract—The integration of semantic communication with Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN)-enabled Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) is a key enabler for 6G, optimizing bandwidth efficiency, Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native inference and intelligent satellite-terrestrial integration. Unlike traditional bit-level transmission, semantic-aware networks extract and transmit only meaningful information, reducing overhead and improving the adaptability. This paper presents SEM-NTN, a semantic-aware O-RAN-enabled NTN framework, that leverages AI-driven feature extraction, adaptive compression, and dynamic resource allocation. Simulation results show that SEM-NTN reduces transmission delay by up to 87.5% while maintaining AI inference accuracy close to that of full-quality compression. Notably, semantic-aware compression achieves up to 84.6% mean Average Precision (mAP) and 77.6% mean Intersection over Union (mIoU) under a 5ms delay constraint—closely matching the uniform baseline (85% mAP, 78% mIoU) but with significantly improved latency performance. These findings highlight SEM-NTN’s potential for scalable, low-latency, and resource-efficient 6G communications. The paper concludes by outlining key challenges in semantic protocol design, real-time adaptation, and standardization for AI-native network integration.

Keywords—semantic communications, non-Terrestrial networks, O-RAN, AI-native networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of 6G is set to revolutionize wireless networks by integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native solutions, Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN), and satellite communications into a seamless, intelligent ecosystem. One of the most promising enablers of this evolution is semantic communications—a transformative approach that goes beyond traditional bit transmission by focusing on the meaning of information rather than its raw data representation [1]. In this new era, networks will not only transmit data more efficiently but will also understand the context and intent behind the information. This capability enables more effective resource allocation, enhanced decision-making, and the dynamic adaptation of network functionalities in real time. By leveraging intelligent semantic communications, 6G systems can optimize spectrum usage and reduce latency, which is especially critical in scenarios where rapid, context-aware responses are necessary—such as in autonomous driving, remote healthcare, and industrial automation [2], [3]. Integrating semantic communications into 6G O-RAN-enabled satellite networks holds the promise of creating truly intelligent communication systems. These systems will be capable of interpreting user needs, prioritizing

mission-critical information, and seamlessly connecting terrestrial, aerial, and space-based assets. However, realizing this vision also brings new challenges, including the development of robust semantic extraction algorithms, ensuring data privacy and security, and managing the complexity of heterogeneous networks that span multiple domains.

The urban environment has various 5G/6G user equipments (UEs) (smartphones, IoT devices, connected cars, and infrastructure sensors) that can rely on semantic communications for low-latency applications [4]. Semantic communication can also be used for intelligent data extraction and transmission. Edge AI computing can be applied to process and optimize data transmission, reducing the need for unnecessary retransmissions and improving system efficiency [5]. The integration of semantic communications with O-RAN and Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) can be a key enabler for next-generation 6G networks, offering intelligent, context-aware, and bandwidth-efficient transmission. Traditional wireless communications focus on maximizing bit-level accuracy, often leading to unnecessary data transmission and increased bandwidth consumption, particularly in satellite-enabled networks where latency and spectral constraints pose significant challenges. Semantic-aware communications shift the paradigm by transmitting only the most relevant and meaningful information, optimizing spectral efficiency and reducing computational overhead. A recent advancement, SEM-O-RAN (Semantic and Flexible O-RAN) framework has demonstrated the potential of semantic-aware slicing for NextG networks [6]. It dynamically adjusts RAN slicing based on the semantic nature of deep learning tasks, reducing transmission overhead while maintaining high inference accuracy.

An evolution from traditional O-RAN components (such as the centralized and distributed units, and the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC)) to an AI-native, semantic-aware architecture, emphasizing the role of semantic processing at the DU level and within the RICs to enhance real-time and control functionalities is given in [7]. The paper in [8] provides a comprehensive overview of semantic communication approaches by categorizing them into four main groups — classical semantic information theory, knowledge graph-based methods, machine learning-based techniques, and significance-based communication — and discusses in detail the strengths, limitations, and open challenges of each approach. In [9], semantic communication is integrated into the Open RAN architecture as an additional semantic layer comprising three new modules — a Semantic Engine, a Semantic RIC (S-RIC)

(a semantically enhanced RIC that hosts intelligent semantic applications) and a CU Semantic Plane (CU-SP) — which, together with improved O-DU and O-RU elements, enable native semantic processing and knowledge-driven control. In contrast to previous work, this paper extends semantic integration beyond conventional terrestrial O-RAN to encompass NTN in the context of SEM-NTN to show that the fusion of satellite and ground infrastructures can further benefit from semantic- control and decision making. This integration can enable more dynamic, knowledge-based resource allocation and interference management across heterogeneous networks, ultimately leading to lower latency, improved energy efficiency and higher reliability in 6G systems.

A. Why Semantic Communications for 6G?

Traditional wireless communication systems are designed to transmit and decode raw data bit by bit, which often leads to significant overhead and inefficiencies. Semantic communication overcomes this bottleneck by applying deep learning and knowledge representation models to extract and transfer only the relevant meaning of data. As a result, it can (i) reduce bandwidth consumption in resource-constrained networks while improving transmission efficiency by eliminating redundant information, (ii) increase resilience to network impairments and attacks, and (iii) enable intelligent decision making at the edge and satellite nodes.

Fig. 1 shows a high-level architecture of SEM-NTN that integrates semantic communications, O-RAN and NTN to create an intelligent satellite-based 6G network. The architecture consists of three key segments: Space, Air Interface and Ground Network demonstrating how semantic-oriented data processing and flexible O-RAN infrastructure work together. In the space segment of the satellite layer, the satellites in orbit can be connected via Inter-Satellite Links (ISLs) and form a dynamic NTN backbone for global coverage. These satellites enable low-latency data routing between different parts of the network. They communicate with ground-based gateways to integrate satellite data into the terrestrial O-RAN infrastructure. The gateway (satellite ground station) serves as an interface between the NTN (satellite system) and the terrestrial O-RAN infrastructure. Data transmission between satellites and ground networks is optimized by semantic communication, which reduces bandwidth consumption by transmitting only relevant information and no raw data. Remote Unit (RU), Distributed Unit (DU) and Central Unit (CU), which are fundamental components of an O-RAN-enabled infrastructure, enable flexible, AI-driven RAN slicing that allows dynamic resource allocation based on user requirements.

B. How Semantic Communications Improve O-RAN enabled NTN?

In space, semantic communication can significantly improve the O-RAN-enabled NTN by intelligently extracting and transmitting only the most meaningful information instead of the entire raw data. This selective transmission can lead to a reduction in data volume, which reduces transmission

Fig. 1: General illustration of semantic communication within the SEM-NTN system where TN and NTN components are natively integrated within 6G networks.

delay and optimizes bandwidth usage — a decisive factor in satellite networks, where capacity can be limited [10]. The integration of semantic processing into the O-RAN framework, in particular via AI-driven RICs can enable dynamic resource allocation and adaptive Radio Access Network (RAN) slicing based on the semantic importance of the transmitted data. This can improve quality of service, reduce latency and enable energy-efficient operation in heterogeneous networks. In addition, semantic communication can be used to enable better interference management and more effective handover between terrestrial and satellite-based connections, ensuring robust connectivity in various 6G scenarios.

This paper presents SEM-NTN, a novel semantic-aware O-RAN-enabled NTN framework that leverages AI-driven feature extraction, adaptive compression, and dynamic RAN slicing for satellite-terrestrial integration. We first outline the general architecture of SEM-NTN, detailing how semantic-aware tuples (namely Semantic-Aware Analytics Engine (SA-AE), Monitoring System (SA-MS) and Semantic-Aware Decision Engine (SA-DE)) interact with O-RAN's RICs to optimize network efficiency. Next, we explore the role of semantic feature prioritization in NTN communications, demonstrating how it enhances low-latency AI inference and real-time decision-making in constrained environments. A case study on SEM-O-RAN for 6G satellite networks is presented, illustrating the effectiveness of semantic-aware slicing in reducing transmission overhead while maintaining high AI accuracy. The proposed SEM-NTN framework provides a scalable, efficient, and AI-driven approach to O-RAN-enabled NTN networks, paving the way for low-latency, energy-efficient, and intelligent satellite-terrestrial communication in 6G. Through extensive simulations and performance evaluations, we compare semantic-aware O-RAN with conventional compression-based NTN solutions, analyzing key metrics such as transmission delay, mAP of AI models, and resource utilization across terrestrial and satellite links. Our results show that SEM-NTN reduces transmission delay by up to 87.5% while achieving 76% AI model accuracy at high bandwidths, making it a highly scalable

and adaptive solution for 6G-integrated TN-NTN networks. Finally, we discuss key challenges and future directions, including real-time semantic model adaptation, security concerns in semantic-aware transmission, and standardization efforts for AI-native O-RAN systems.

II. SEMANTIC COMMUNICATIONS FOR O-RAN-ENABLED SATELLITE NETWORKS

The O-RAN architecture, with its open interfaces and intelligent controllers (RICs), can provide a perfect foundation for implementing semantic-aware satellite-integrated networks. In 6G O-RAN satellite networks, this capability can be critical for mission-critical applications such as autonomous vehicles, remote sensing, Internet of Things (IoT) and space-to-ground communications, where latency, reliability and efficiency are paramount. Fig. 2 presents a multi-layer Semantic-Aware (SA)-aware O-RAN architecture integrating Terrestrial Network (TN) and NTN while incorporating AI-driven semantic-aware decision-making for optimized mobility, quality-of-service (QoS), and interference management. The architecture consists of three main layers: (i) SA O-RAN Management Layer, (ii) SA O-RAN Control Layer and (iii) SA O-RAN Functions Layer (Radio & Processing Units). Each layer integrates AI-based analytics, monitoring, decision-making, and semantic-aware processing.

At the SA O-RAN Management Layer, the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) module governs network configurations, policies, and AI-driven decision-making. This layer also includes the Non-Real-Time RIC, which focuses on long-term AI model training, resource optimization, and policy enforcement. The integration of SA modules allows the network to extract meaningful information from raw data, reducing unnecessary transmissions and improving efficiency. SA-driven AI optimization can ensure efficient handover management, interference mitigation and resource allocation, making this architecture highly scalable, adaptable and optimized for future 6G NTN-TN hybrid networks. The SA O-RAN Control Layer is responsible for near-real-time control and adaptation through the Near-RT RIC. This layer implements AI-driven models for mobility management, QoS optimization, and interference mitigation. The SA O-RAN functional layer consists of the central O-RAN infrastructure, including the integrated O-CU, O-DU and O-RU. These components can handle radio resource scheduling, Medium Access Control (MAC)/Radio Link Control (RLC) processing and the RF/PHY layer operations for both terrestrial and satellite-based O-RAN nodes. The Open Fronthaul Interface can enable seamless integration between TN (such as O-RAN cellular base stations) and NTN (such as satellite communication gateways) and thus dynamic routing of data based on real-time network conditions.

All components (including Non-Real-Time and Near-RT RIC) dynamically interact with the SA-DE, SA-AE, SA-MS, and Actuator (ACT), forming a closed-loop AI-powered optimization system. The SA-MS gathers network state information from both terrestrial and satellite O-RAN nodes. It can also apply semantic feature extraction to determine which data is important and which can be discarded. Therefore,

instead of raw transmission of massive data, it can collect high-value contextual data (e.g., key patterns in interference, mobility behavior). The SA-AE in Fig. 2 is an AI-driven optimization module designed to enhance network efficiency in O-RAN-enabled TN-NTN. The SA-AE processes the extracted semantic data using AI and deep learning models. It further enhances analytics process by prioritizing meaningful information instead of transmitting raw data, optimizing spectrum use, reducing bandwidth consumption and improving quality of service and computational overhead for latency-sensitive applications. It can identify traffic patterns, network congestion trends, or predictive mobility events (e.g., detecting when a UE moves between satellite and terrestrial links). Both SA-MS and SA-AE can significantly reduce network overhead by processing only relevant information. The SA-DE uses machine learning models, reinforcement learning, and game-theoretic approaches to (i) dynamically allocate spectrum and power resources between NTN and TN, (ii) adjust RAN resource policies based on user/service demand and (iii) optimize compression ratios for semantic-aware data transmission. This results in smarter, adaptive O-RAN control with minimal signaling overhead. Finally, the ACT applies optimized configurations in real-time by: (i) reconfiguring Integrated O-Centralized Unit (O-CU), O-Distributed Unit (O-DU), and O-Radio Unit (O-RU) units for better resource allocation. (ii) adjusting satellite-to-ground bandwidth dynamically and (ii) enabling interference mitigation strategies in dense NTN-TN environments.

Fig. 2: Semantic-aware closed loop management and control with tuples (SA-MS, SA-AE, SA-DE and ACT) in integrated NTNs and TNs within SEM-NTN framework.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Experiment Setting: Metrics and Parameters

In evaluating semantic communication and related AI-driven wireless networks, several key metrics are used to assess the trade-offs in systems where traditional performance metrics (such as raw accuracy and delay) are augmented by the need for intelligent, meaning-based data transmission. mAP is a widely used performance indicator in object recognition. It is calculated as the average precision across all object classes and

indicates how well a model correctly identifies and localizes objects. A higher mAP means better detection accuracy. mIoU is used in image segmentation to measure the overlap between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth. It is calculated by dividing the intersection of the predicted and actual regions by their union and then averaging across all classes. Higher mIoU values indicate better segmentation accuracy. Transmission delay quantifies the time it takes for data to travel from source to destination over a network. In the context of satellite communication and semantic transmission, a lower delay is crucial for real-time applications, especially when bandwidth is limited.

For simulations, we first load CIFAR-10 training images and uses the first 1000 images [11]. We set a target average size of 100 KB to be consistent with the SEM-O-RAN assumption (since the SEM-O-RAN metrics assume that the uncompressed image is around 100 KB) [6]. Then we define realistic metrics from the SEM-O-RAN paper as given in Table I which presents the impact of compression on AI model performance, specifically for object detection (YOLOX [12]) and image segmentation (BiSeNet V2 [13]). The Compression Factor (τ) represents the level of compression applied to images, where higher values (e.g., 1.00) indicate no compression (full-quality images), while lower values (e.g., 0.04) correspond to high compression, significantly reducing image quality. The image size (KB) column shows how file size decreases as compression increases, with full-quality images ($\tau = 1.00$) being 100 KB, whereas highly compressed images ($\tau = 0.04$) shrink to just 2.3 KB. This reduction conserves bandwidth but at the cost of AI model accuracy. For object detection, the mAP of YOLOX decreases as compression intensifies. At $\tau = 1.00$, mAP remains high at 0.85, ensuring accurate object recognition. However, at $\tau = 0.04$, mAP drops sharply to 0.10, indicating severe degradation in detection performance due to compression artifacts. Similarly, the mIoU for image segmentation using BiSeNet V2 follows a similar trend. At $\tau = 1.00$, mIoU is 0.78, reflecting strong segmentation accuracy. However, at $\tau = 0.04$, mIoU plummets to 0.12, demonstrating that excessive compression distorts segmentation boundaries and reduces model effectiveness. We simulate 1000 transmissions. Lower and upper bound for simulation-domain compression factor are selected to be 0.2 and 1.0 respectively and MAX_TX_DELAY is fixed at 2ms. In the simulation, MAX_TX_DELAY represents the maximum allowable allowable transmission delay within the semantic pipeline, excluding propagation delay across the satellite link.

TABLE I: Compression Scaling Factor vs. AI Accuracy in SEM-O-RAN Metrics [6].

Factor (τ)	Size (KB)	mAP (YOLOX)	mIoU (BiSeNetV2)
1.00	100.0	0.85	0.78
0.47	29.5	0.60	0.55
0.20	10.0	0.35	0.35
0.04	2.3	0.10	0.12

We define per-user Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite link capacities from 100 Mbps to 1 Gbps [14]. Allowed image size

to be transmitted is calculated by multiplying LEO satellite link capacity and MAX_TX_DELAY. For each of the 1000 simulations, we do the following: First, we randomly choose one scaled CIFAR-10 image size (which averages 100 KB). Second, we compute a desired simulation-domain compression factor based on the random semantic complexity and convert the simulation-domain factor into a realistic compression factor and get the mAP corresponding to the realistic compression factor as in Table I. For uniform detailed compression (i.e., no compression), the realistic compression factor is 1.0. The compressed image size is just the original (scaled) size and the mAP is obtained by interpolating at a compression factor of 1.0 (which is 85%). For each link capacity, transmission delay is computed as compressed image size (KB) divided by link bandwidth (KB/s) for both the semantic-aware compression and the uniform detailed baseline. In our simulations, semantic complexity is not computed directly from image content, but is instead modeled as a random variable uniformly sampled for each image to represent the variability in scene richness. This abstraction enables controlled evaluation of how semantic-aware compression strategies adapt under different perceived complexity levels. In a real deployment, semantic complexity could be estimated from the output of lightweight object detection or scene understanding models (e.g., YOLOX), using features such as the number of detected objects, confidence scores, and spatial distribution of detections. These features would inform the selection between aggressive and detailed compression, allowing dynamic adjustment to task-relevant content.

B. Results

In semantic-aware compression with delay constraint, we first compute a desired compression factor for each image based on its semantic complexity (using linear interpolation). We then calculate the delay if this compression would be used. In order to maintain a MAX_TX_DELAY of 2 ms, we determine the maximum compression factor allowed at the current link capacity. The effective compression factor is the minimum of the desired factor and the allowed factor. This means that if the link capacity is low, the system is forced to compress more aggressively (lower effective factor) in order to reach the delay threshold, which in turn reduces accuracy. As the capacity of the satellite link increases, the delay naturally decreases and the system can afford to use the semantically desired (higher) compression factors, resulting in better accuracy.

Fig. 3 compares the transmission delay and inference accuracy (mAP) between semantic-aware (adaptive) compression and a baseline uniform detailed compression strategy across varying LEO satellite bandwidths. In semantic-aware compression, the compression level is dynamically adapted based on the semantic relevance of image content: (i) Aggressive compression is applied when the semantic complexity is low (i.e., scenes with “simple” or less relevant objects), which significantly reduces the image size and transmission delay but results in lower inference accuracy. (ii) Detailed compression is applied when semantic complexity is high, preserving more

visual detail to support accurate inference, albeit with slightly increased image size and transmission delay. In Fig. 3, the left y-axis shows the average transmission delay per image, while the right y-axis shows the average inference accuracy. As the LEO satellite bandwidth increases in Fig. 3, the transmission delay decreases for both methods, but semantic-aware compression consistently achieves lower delays across all bandwidth levels. As shown in the figure, semantic-aware compression consistently maintains lower delay across all bandwidth levels, while the inference accuracy improves with increasing bandwidth—eventually reaching parity with uniform compression at around 1000 Mbps. In contrast, uniform compression maintains constant accuracy but incurs significantly higher delay, especially at lower bandwidths. At 100 Mbps, the transmission delay using semantic-aware compression is approximately 0.0001s, compared to 0.0080s for uniform detailed compression, representing a 87.5% reduction in delay. At 200 Mbps, semantic-aware compression remains around 0.0010s, while uniform compression drops to 0.0040s, maintaining a 75% improvement. As bandwidth increases further, the delay gap narrows gradually; for example, at 500 Mbps, semantic-aware compression still holds at approximately 0.0010s, while uniform compression is around 0.0016s, resulting in a 37.5% advantage. At 1000 Mbps, semantic-aware delay stays near 0.0010s, while uniform compression drops to 0.0008s, slightly reversing the gap but still within a comparable range. In terms of accuracy, semantic-aware compression initially leads to lower mAP, starting at approximately 38% at 100 Mbps and steadily increasing to about 85% at 1000 Mbps, eventually matching the performance of uniform compression, which maintains a constant mAP of 85% across all bandwidths since it does not degrade information.

Fig. 3: Comparison of transmission delay with the capacity of LEO satellite links (using CIFAR-10) for semantic and uniform compression.

Fig. 4 shows the accuracy metrics—object detection mAP and segmentation mIoU—as a function of MAX_TX_DELAY under a fixed satellite bandwidth of 500 Mbps. In this performance simulations, tight MAX_TX_DELAY constraints such as 0.5–5ms are imposed to test compression strategies under pressure, reflect edge-to-edge (device-to-device via satellite)

inference timing and explore feasibility for future ultra-reliable low-latency communication over NTN. At a very tight delay constraint of 0.5 ms, the semantic-aware mAP is approximately 60.5%, and the mIoU is around 55.6%, reflecting the impact of aggressive compression required to meet the stringent latency target. As the MAX_TX_DELAY increases, the system can afford to use less aggressive compression, which improves accuracy significantly. At around 1 ms, the mAP surpasses 72% and mIoU reaches 65%. By 2 ms, mAP approaches 84.6%, and mIoU rises to 77.6%, nearly matching the performance of uniform compression, which remains constant at 85% mAP and 78% mIoU. These results highlight that with relaxed delay constraints, semantic-aware compression can closely approximate full-quality performance while still benefiting from lower data transmission costs, making it highly suitable for adaptive satellite communication scenarios.

Fig. 4: The accuracy metrics versus MAX_TX_DELAY for fixed satellite bandwidth of 500 Mbps.

IV. DISCUSSIONS

This simulation provided a basic framework to study the trade-offs between bandwidth usage and inference accuracy under varying network conditions. Semantic-aware compression can significantly reduce transmission delay (up to 87.5% at 100 Mbps), while allowing the mAP to improve with increasing bandwidth, making it highly effective for bandwidth-constrained satellite networks. However, it sacrifices AI model accuracy at lower bandwidths. At low bandwidth levels (100–300 Mbps), semantic compression results in lower AI accuracy (approximately 38–63% mAP) but provides significant latency gains over uniform compression. As bandwidth increases to 500–1000 Mbps, the mAP steadily improves, eventually reaching 85%, effectively matching the accuracy of uniform compression. Results showed that under lower satellite link capacities, the enforced aggressive compression (to meet delay constraints) leads to lower inference accuracy. Conversely, at higher capacities, the system can use less aggressive compression and thus achieve better accuracy while keeping delays within acceptable limits. On the other hand, uniform compression maintains high accuracy but at the cost of higher delays, which may limit its practicality for real-time or latency-sensitive NTN applications.

Note that SA-related modules can also be introduced at the O-DU and O-RU, but not a separate one at the O-CU as in reference [7]. This is because the semantic processing enhancements can be most beneficial at the DU/RU level. For example, the O-DU is responsible for handling real-time, lower-layer tasks (RLC/MAC/PHY-high) that directly process the raw and minimally processed data and thus benefit from incorporating semantic awareness and reasoning capabilities. In contrast, the O-CU primarily deals with higher-layer control and protocol functions that do not require the same kind of real-time semantic processing. However, semantic intelligence is incorporated for example, in the SA RICs, which are designed to manage the overall intent and context without modifying the core higher-layer CU functions. The integration of semantic communication into O-RAN-based NTN also requires a rethinking of functional split strategies. By embedding semantic engines and AI-based RIC functionalities onboard satellites, the network can become more intelligent, delay-tolerant, and bandwidth-efficient. An example split in [15] is proposed where core O-RAN components such as the radio unit, distributed unit and centralized unit are used on board satellites and form a Space-O-RAN framework coordinated by an on-board Space-RIC. This configuration can enable AI-driven semantic applications and deterministic applications to process data directly in space, utilizing local compute resources such as GPUs and FPGAs, and making real-time decisions before transmitting to the ground. On the terrestrial side, the SMO system and the NTN non-real-time RIC are responsible for global coordination, AI model distribution, policy enforcement, and configuration management. These terrestrial entities interact with the Space-RIC through flexible link mapping, maintaining synchronization and end-to-end control. However, other functional split options are also conceivable, in which future systems could use adaptive, context-aware splits depending on mission objectives, latency requirements and hardware capacities. For example, semantic compression can be done onboard during congestion, or deferred to the terrestrial side during idle periods. This flexibility is in line with the modular, software-defined vision of O-RAN and ensures efficient satellite-based terrestrial integration.

V. CHALLENGES AND THE ROAD AHEAD FOR 6G WITH SEMANTIC-AWARE INTEGRATED NETWORKS

Although the term "semantic communication" is not yet explicitly used in the standardization bodies, there is growing interest from research and industry in the integration of AI approaches - including semantic data processing — into future 6G architectures. For this reason, AI-native semantic communication can be used in future 6G architectures to improve NTN integration with O-RAN-based architectures and to explore network slicing and edge AI optimizations for efficient communication. As research progresses, collaboration between academia, industry and standardization bodies (3GPP, O-RAN Alliance, ITU-T, IEEE and others) will also be crucial in defining the future of SA integrated TN/NTN 6G systems. At the same time, although semantic communication offers promising advantages, there are also still some questions/challenges that need to be addressed:

- How can we integrate semantic-aware protocols into existing O-RAN standards?
- Can semantic slicing policies be universally applied across terrestrial and satellite networks?
- How do we ensure that AI-based semantic encoders/decoders generalize well across diverse network environments?
- What are the trade-offs between model complexity, interpretability, and computational cost?
- How can we prevent adversarial attacks on AI-driven semantic encoders?
- What are the implications of privacy-preserving semantic communication?
- How can we optimize low-power AI inference for semantic communications in space-based systems?
- Can advanced techniques such as neuromorphic computing enhance energy-efficient semantic processing?

Semantic communication systems also introduce new vulnerabilities to adversarial attacks, particularly through manipulated semantic features or poisoned inputs targeting neural encoders. To mitigate these risks, techniques such as adversarially robust training and semantic consistency checks using knowledge graphs or anomaly detection can enhance the trustworthiness of task-level inference under attack conditions. While CIFAR-10 was used to demonstrate core concepts, the proposed semantic-aware compression framework is modular and can scale to high-resolution satellite imagery or video by employing region-based semantic estimation and adaptive tiling. For the future, more advanced and lightweight inference models (e.g., MobileNet, Swin Transformer) can be integrated to handle the increased complexity without sacrificing real-time processing. Additionally, the development of a multi-layer semantic stack model which includes the interactions between the protocols of the lower layers and semantic-aware scheduling in the data plane, hardware-in-the-loop evaluations integration with open-source O-RAN platforms (e.g., OAI or srsRAN) are of interest.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a comprehensive study of semantic communications within the context of O-RAN-enabled Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN), introducing a scalable and AI-driven framework—SEM-NTN—designed to meet the stringent requirements of 6G satellite-terrestrial integration. By leveraging semantic-aware architecture, intelligent RAN resource allocation, and AI-enhanced control via the RIC, SEM-NTN enables efficient, adaptive bandwidth utilization and low-latency communication across heterogeneous networks. Simulation results demonstrated that semantic-aware communication can reduce transmission delay by up to 87.5% while achieving AI inference accuracy close to that of full-quality (uniform) transmission, particularly under relaxed delay constraints and high bandwidth conditions. Furthermore, the results showed that semantic-aware systems can dynamically adapt to link conditions and latency budgets, achieving 84.6% mAP and 77.6% mIoU with an allowable delay of 5ms, almost matching the performance of conventional

uniform compression. These results confirm the feasibility of semantic communication as a fundamental component in future 6G O-RAN and NTN architectures, especially for real-time, bandwidth-constrained and AI-native applications. The proposed architecture and performance analysis highlight the potential of SEM-NTN to enable intelligent, delay-sensitive and energy-efficient communications and pave the way for the next generation of 6G satellite-based networks.

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